

Report D2.3 "Report on OCES Disciplines of Interest"

Grant Agreement: 958371

OntoCommons - Ontology-driven data documentation for Industry Commons, has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 958371.

Project Title	Ontology-driven data documentation for Industry Commons
Project Acronym	OntoCommons
Project Number	958371
Type of project	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topics	DT-NMBP-39-2020 - Towards Standardised Documentation of Data through taxonomies and ontologies (CSA)
Starting date of Project	01 November 2020
Duration of the project	36 months
Website	www.ontocommons.eu

Report D2.3

“Report on OCES Disciplines of Interest”

Work Package	WP2 Top Reference Ontology
Task	T2.3 Definition of the Disciplines of Interest
Lead author	Emanuele Ghedini (UNIBO)
Contributors	Stefano Borgo (CNR), Ana Correia (ATB), Arkopaul Sarkar (ENIT), Claudio Masolo (CNR)
Peer reviewers	Hedi Karray (ENIT)
Version	Final
Date	04/11/2021

Versioning History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	08/10/2021	Emanuele Ghedini	Creation of report first version.
0.2	27/10/2021	Emanuele Ghedini	Draft with complete analysis.

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
TLO	<p>Top Level Ontology.</p> <p>A top-level ontology (or foundation ontology) is an ontology (in the sense used in information science) which consists of very general terms (such as "object", "property", "relation") that are common across all domains.</p>
MLO	<p>Middle Level Ontologies.</p> <p>Mid-level ontologies are primarily intended to extend those concepts towards a specific discipline (e.g. manufacturing, materials science, chemistry) with the aim to provide a core shared vocabulary for lower level modules. A MLO will provide a higher level of detail than a TLO, extending the taxonomical structure of the ontology more along on the horizontal dimension (i.e. sibling classes under the same superclass).</p>
DLO	<p>Domain Level Ontology.</p> <p>A domain-level ontology is one that identifies types that further specialize the basic types from one or more mid-level ontologies. Domain ontologies describe objects, events, and relationships that are of interest to a more limited number of knowledge domains (e.g., Intelligent Analyst Role, Portion of Ammonium Nitrate, or Act of Watercraft Registration).</p>

Keywords

Scientific Disciplines, Middle Level Ontology.

Disclaimer

OntoCommons (958371) is a Coordination & Support Action funded by the European Commission under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Horizon 2020 (H2020). This document contains information on researched by OntoCommons Beneficiaries. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation, and publication date. The document has been produced with the funding of the European Commission. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the OntoCommons Consortium, and it cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission. The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

Executive Summary

The objective of T2.3 is to analyse the outcomes of WP1, WP3, WP4 and WP5 to identify the general disciplines (i.e., scientific fields such as chemistry and manufacturing) to be addressed by the MLOs within the OCES. This is done by:

- a) the identification of the general disciplines of interest of the Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 *5.ii. Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing* (NMBP) work programme¹
- b) the disciplines needed specifically by the OntoCommons demonstrators.

Following WP3, the classification of scientific domains provided by the German Research Foundation (DFG)². Each NMBP calls and OntoCommons demonstrators is related to Scientific Disciplines and Area in order to provide an overview of the most relevant sectors and define a priority list of the disciplines to be covered by the OCES to achieve demonstrators' objectives is proposed.

Disciplines are then analysed to define the possible role and scope of MLOs, according to concepts commonalities between Area and Sub-Area within the same Scientific Discipline.

¹https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2018-2020/main/h2020-wp1820-leit-nmp_en.pdf

²https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/dfg_im_profil/gremien/fachkollegien/amtperiode_2016_2019/fachsystematik_2016-2019_en_grafik.pdf

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	6
1.1 Methodology.....	6
2. Definition of the Disciplines of Interest.....	8
2.1 NMBP Work Programme Analysis.....	8
2.1.1 Humanities Sub-Areas.....	9
2.1.2 Life Sciences Sub-Areas.....	10
2.1.3 Natural Sciences Sub-Areas.....	10
2.1.4 Engineering Sciences Sub-Areas.....	11
2.2 OntoCommons Demonstrators Disciplines.....	12
3. Disciplines Priority List.....	14
4. Conclusions.....	16

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Extended DWG scientific disciplines and fields.....	7
Figure 2 - Scientific Discipline Recurrency in NMBP H2020 WP.....	8
Figure 3 - Research Area Recurrency in NMBP H2020 WP.....	9
Figure 4 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Humanities.....	10
Figure 5 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Life Sciences.....	10
Figure 6 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Natural Sciences.....	11
Figure 7 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Engineering Sciences.....	12

1. Introduction

1.1 Methodology

The first thing to define is the concept of discipline, that in the DoA is described as very general scientific fields, such as chemistry and manufacturing. The concept of disciplines is used in OntoCommons to identify high-level domains of interest that are many specific application fields. Disciplines are also used to define the concept of Middle Level Ontology (MLO).

In fact, while Top Level Ontologies (TLO) provide a formal characterization of general concepts according to specific ontological perspectives, MLOs are primarily intended to extend those concepts towards a specific discipline (e.g. manufacturing, materials science, chemistry) with the aim to provide a core shared vocabulary for lower level act as foundations for lower level modules. A MLO will provide a higher level of detail than a TLO, extending the taxonomical structure of the ontology more along on the horizontal dimension (i.e. sibling classes under the same superclass).

Following WP3, the classification of scientific domains provided by the German Research Foundation (DFG) will be used as reference for discipline taxonomy in order to retain compatibility between WP2 and WP3. A slightly extended disciplines list with respect to the one used in D3.2 is shown in Figure 1.

Following call text analysis of the Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 5.ii. *Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing* (NMBP), the list of disciplines overlapping each call topic are identified and reported, to underline the most needed ones in terms of priority. The match between the topic and the discipline is done analysing call keywords and finding the best matches within the sub-area and subject area (not shown here) titles and description following the DFG categorization.

A similar approach will be used for OntoCommons demonstrators' relevant disciplines.

A priority list is then proposed, together with a list of some relevant non-ontological knowledge reference points (e.g. standards, organization) for each discipline, that can be used to define their respective domain of interest and vocabulary.

Scientific discipline	Research area	Research sub-area	Reference DFG code	Reference ERC code	
Humanities and Social Sciences			1		
	Humanities		11		
		Ancient Culture	101		
		History	102		
		Fine Arts, Music, Theatre and Media Studies	103		
		Philosophy	108		
	Social and Behavioural Sciences		12		
		Educational Research	109		
		Psychology	110		
		Social Sciences	111		
		Economics	112		
		Jurisprudence	113		
	Life Science			2	
Biology			21		
		Basic Biological and Medical Research	201		
Medicine			22		
	Medicine	205			
Natural Sciences			3		
	Chemistry		31		
		Molecular Chemistry	301		
		Chemical Solid State and Surface Research (incl. Characterisation)	302		
		Physical and Theoretical Chemistry	303		
		Analytical Chemistry, Method Development (Chemistry)	304		
		Biological Chemistry and Food Chemistry	305		
		Polymer Research	306		
	Physics		32		
		Condensed Matter Physics	307		
		Optics, Quantum Optics and Physics of Atoms, Molecules and Plasmas	308		
		Statistical Physics, Soft Matter, Biological Physics, Nonlinear Dynamics	310		
	Engineering sciences			4	
		Mechanical and industrial engineering		41	
Production technology (incl. Quality Control)			401		
Mechanics and constructive mechanical engineering			402		
Thermal Engineering/Process Engineering			42		
		Process engineering, technical chemistry	403		
		Heat energy technology, thermal machines, fluid mechanics	404		
Material Science and Engineering			43		
		Materials engineering	405		
		Material Science	406		
		Industrial bioengineering		PE8_14	
Computer science, systems and electrical engineering		Industrial biofuel production		PE8_15	
			44		
		Simulation engineering and modelling		PE7-3	
		Networks (communication networks, sensor networks, networks of robots...)		PE7-8	
		Systems engineering	407		
		Electrical Engineering and Information Technology	408		
Construction Engineering and Architecture		Computer Science	409		
		45			
	Construction Engineering	410			

Figure 1 - Extended DWG scientific disciplines and fields

2. Definition of the Disciplines of Interest

2.1 NMBP Work Programme Analysis

The main scientific disciplines intersecting the 38 NMBP calls within the Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 5.ii. *Nanotechnologies, Advanced Materials, Biotechnology and Advanced Manufacturing and Processing* (NMBP) are shown in Figure 2. A larger reference to Engineering sciences is evidenced with respect to Natural sciences, due to the applicative nature of the WP. Life Sciences and Humanities play an important role in few calls, but are rarely referred in the majority of the calls text.

More details on the Research Area recurrency are shown in Figure 3 for each discipline. **Material Sciences and Engineering** and **Computer Sciences** are the predominant Research Areas, followed by **Chemistry**. This is related to the strong emphasis towards materials and their uptake in the European industry, together with the need for a better usage of digitalization techniques and approaches in terms of modelling, data documentation, sharing and reuse, and sensing systems. **Physics, Mechanical and Industrial Engineering** and **Process Engineering** seem almost equally relevant.

Figure 2 - Scientific Discipline Recurrency in NMBP H2020 WP

Figure 3 - Research Area Recurrency in NMBP H2020 WP

2.1.1 Humanities Sub-Areas

The intersection of the NMBP H2020 WP is mainly due to the NMBP-21-2020 and NMBP-33-2018 calls, that explicitly requires interactions with Social Sciences and Humanities while dealing with sensitive medical related topics and cultural heritage. **Educational Research** and **Jurisprudence** are the most recurring sub-areas as shown in Figure 4.

Scientific discipline	Research area	Research sub-area	Reference DFG code	Reference ERC code	Recurrency
Humanities and Social Sciences			1		14
	Humanities		11		4
		Ancient Culture	101		1
		History	102		1
		Fine Arts, Music, Theatre and Media Studies	103		1
		Philosophy	108		1
	Social and Behavioural Sciences		12		10
		Educational Research	109		3
		Psychology	110		1
		Social Sciences	111		1
		Economics	112		1
		Jurisprudence	113		4

Figure 4 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Humanities

2.1.2 Life Sciences Sub-Areas

References to **Basic Biology and Medical Research** and **Medicine** are found mainly within the Medical Technology Innovation and Risk Assessment and Regulatory topics. Their recurrency is shown in Figure 5.

Scientific discipline	Research area	Research sub-area	Reference DFG code	Reference ERC code	Recurrency
Life Science			2		17
	Biology		21		5
		Basic Biological and Medical Research	201		5
	Medicine		22		12
		Medicine	205		12

Figure 5 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Life Sciences

2.1.3 Natural Sciences Sub-Areas

In the Chemistry research area, the most referred sub-area is the **Chemical Solid State and Surface Research** mainly due to its intersection with nanomaterial sciences, and for material characterization, material synthesis and modelling. **Biological and Biomimetic Chemistry** is also required by several calls that focus on the safety and regulation of nanomaterials.

In the Physics research area, the most referred sub-area is **Condensed Matter Physics**, related to calls focusing on material development and characterization.

The recurrences are shown in Figure 6.

Scientific discipline	Research area	Research sub-area	Reference DFG code	Reference ERC code	Recurrency
Natural Sciences			3		87
	Chemistry		31		59
		Molecular Chemistry	301		8
		Chemical Solid State and Surface Research (incl. Characterisation)	302		31
		Physical and Theoretical Chemistry	303		5
		Analytical Chemistry, Method Development (Chemistry)	304		2
		Biological Chemistry and Food Chemistry	305		11
		Polymer Research	306		2
	Physics		32		28
		Condensed Matter Physics	307		26
		Optics, Quantum Optics and Physics of Atoms, Molecules and Plasmas	308		1
		Statistical Physics, Soft Matter, Biological Physics, Nonlinear Dynamics	310		1

Figure 6 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Natural Sciences

2.1.4 Engineering Sciences Sub-Areas

In the Mechanical and Industrial Engineering research area, the most referred sub-area is **Production Technology**, mostly related to production and operation management, and quality control, through almost all the calls.

For similar reasons, the **Process Engineering and Technical Chemistry** is the most referred sub-area under Thermal and Process Engineering, due to the requirement of developing effective production methods and usage of materials in the industry that spans through several topics.

Material Science and **Materials Engineering** are clearly the mostly referred sub-area due to the material-oriented nature of the H2020 NMBP WP, that encompass both the research and the engineering aspects of the material field.

In the research area of Computer Science, the mostly cited sub-area is **System Engineering**, especially related to measurement and control systems, followed by **Computer Science** due to the prominent push for digitalization that characterize the WP, especially related to software engineering, databases, process, and knowledge management. **Simulation and Modelling**, together with **Networks** (sensing) are also often cited in the WP.

Construction Engineering is referred only by a couple of calls, especially related to bridges safety and cultural heritage conservation.

Scientific discipline	Research area	Research sub-area	Reference DFG code	Reference ERC code	Recurrency	
Engineering sciences			4		209	
	Mechanical and industrial engineering		41		34	
		Production technology (incl. Quality Control)	401		27	
		Mechanics and constructive mechanical engineering	402		7	
	Thermal Engineering/Process Engineering		42		30	
		Process engineering, technical chemistry	403		28	
		Heat energy technology, thermal machines, fluid mechanics	404		2	
	Material Science and Engineering		43		72	
		Materials engineering	405		31	
		Material Science	406		31	
		Industrial bioengineering		PE8_14	9	
	Computer science, systems and electrical engineering	Industrial biofuel production			PE8_15	1
			44		71	
		Simulation engineering and modelling			PE7-3	11
		Networks (communication networks, sensor networks, networks of robots...)			PE7-8	12
		Systems engineering	407		23	
		Electrical Engineering and Information Technology	408		6	
	Construction Engineering and Architecture	Computer Science	409		19	
			45		2	
		Construction Engineering	410		2	

Figure 7 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for Engineering Sciences

2.2 OntoCommons Demonstrators Disciplines

Following the OntoCommons DoA and the WP5 D5.2 activities, an analysis of the recurrency of the disciplines has been carried out for the initial demonstrators:

- UC1 IRIS - Industrial Co-design Support
- UC2: SeDIM: Semantic Data Integration for Manufacturing
- UC3: Engineering for Procurement
- UC4: Materials' Tribological Characterisation
- UC5: EVMF - European Virtual Marketplace Framework
- UC6: OAS
- UC7: Feedstock Quality Assurance
- UC8: Nanomaterials Characterisation
- UC9: Ontology-based Maintenance
- UC10: Data Integration and Interoperability in Manufacturing
- UC11: Digital Manufacturing / Complex Equipment

Results are shown in Figure 8.

Scientific discipline	Research area	Research sub-area	Reference DFG code	Reference ERC code	Recurrency	
Life Science			2		1	
	Biology		21		0	
	Medicine		22		1	
Medicine			205		1	
Natural Sciences			3		6	
	Chemistry		31		6	
		Chemical Solid State and Surface Research (incl. Characterisation)		302		6
	Physics		32		0	
Engineering sciences			4		47	
	Mechanical and industrial engineering		41		6	
		Production technology (incl. Quality Control)		401		6
	Thermal Engineering/Process Engineering		42		8	
		Process engineering, technical chemistry		403		8
	Material Science and Engineering		43		13	
		Materials engineering		405		6
		Material Science		406		7
	Computer science, systems and electrical engineering			44		20
		Simulation engineering and modelling			PE7-3	4
		Networks (communication networks, sensor networks, networks of robots...)			PE7-8	1
		Systems engineering		407		6
		Technology		408		1
Computer Science			409		8	

Figure 8 - Research Area and Sub-Area recurrency for OntoCommons initial demonstrators

Even with a largely lower number of cases to analyse with respect to the H2020 NMBP WP, recurrences are in percentage similar, with a higher recurrency of the Computer Science in the OntoCommons demonstrators due to the nature of the project, which is focused on ontologies (i.e., knowledge management) that fall under this discipline scope.

Figure 9 – Discipline recurrency for NMBP WP and OntoCommons demonstrators

3. Disciplines Priority List

According to the previous analysis it is possible to identify the specific disciplines that should be addressed by the OCES MLOs collection, to provide the wider and more effective coverage of the NMBP topics.

Moreover, for each discipline/subject-area, a preliminary list of resource materials that can help to identify concepts and languages is provided:

- **Concepts References:** existing non-ontologised domain of interest resources that provides an organic set of concept definitions and terminology (e.g., IUPAC Goldbook, CIF vocabulary)
- **Languages:** existing resources providing well defined methodologies for knowledge representation (e.g., data formats) and interpretation (e.g., international system of quantities, mathematics, data formats, DCAT, IDS)

This list and resource materials can be used within T2.5 to start building a conceptual map of a possible mid-level discipline-oriented structure.

Sub-Area	#	Concepts References (e.g., vocabulary, definitions)	Languages
Materials Sciences and Engineering	62	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CIF Crystallographic Information Framework - IUCR online Dictionary of Crystallography - NIST Materials Resource Registry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CIF Dictionary
Chemical Solid State and Surface Research (including Characterisation)	31	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology - International vocabulary of metrology – Basic and general concepts and associated terms (VIM) - CIF Crystallographic Information Framework - IUCR online Dictionary of Crystallography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EMCC CHADA - ISO 80000 Quantities and units - The International System of Units (SI) - CIF Dictionary
Process Engineering	28	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management Life cycle assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lifecycle modelling language (LML)
Production Technology (including Quality Control)	27	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO 9000:2015 Quality management systems 	n.a.
Condensed Matter Physics	26	(see Materials Sci. and Eng. And Chem. Solid State and Surf. Research)	(see Materials Sci. and Eng. And Chem. Solid State and Surf. Research)
System Engineering	23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IEC 81346-1:2009 Industrial systems, installations and equipment and industrial products - SEVOCAB: Software and Systems Engineering Vocabulary 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systems Modelling Language (SysML)
Computer Science (Software Engineering, Operating, Communication, Database and Distributed Systems, Interactive and Intelligent Systems, Image and Language Processing, Computer Graphics and Visualisation, Information Systems, Process and Knowledge Management)	19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SEVOCAB: Software and Systems Engineering Vocabulary - ISO/IEC 27000:2018 Information technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)
Networks (communication networks, sensor networks, networks of robots...)	12	n.a.	n.a.

Medicine (toxicology, biomedical technology and medical physics, pharmacology)	12	n.a.	n.a.
Simulation engineering and modelling	11	- EC Review of Materials Modelling (RoMM)	- EMMC MODA
Biological Chemistry and Food Chemistry	11	n.a.	n.a.

4. Conclusions

- Mention the most cited
- Lack of organic vocabularies for the some of the most relevant disciplines
- it seems that the wider the discipline is, than concepts definitions are left to discipline common interpretation (good for the sector, but not good for interoperability)
- multiple vocabularies with often overlapping definitions